

1 Experimental Assessment of Material Resistance to 2 Freshwater Biofouling

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8 Abstract

9 This study outlines a comprehensive, multi-stage, multi-scale experimental framework for evaluating material
10 resistance to freshwater biofouling. The research integrates a variety of technologies, including high-resolution
11 digital cameras, High-Speed Structured Illumination Microscopy, Atomic Force Microscopy, confocal laser
12 microscopy, and Scanning Electron Microscopy, to provide an all-encompassing understanding of biofouling
13 dynamics from macro to micro scales. While this approach marks significant advancements in the field, it also poses
14 certain challenges, such as technological limitations inherent to each experimental phase and the complexity of
15 managing multi-faceted data. Future research directions aim to address these constraints by incorporating more
16 advanced imaging technologies and data analytics techniques. In summary, this study serves as a foundational guide
17 for future research, establishing a standardized methodology for assessing and preventing freshwater biofouling.

18 *Keywords:* Biofouling; Freshwater; Material resistance; Experimental assessment; Microscope

19 Biofouling, often termed as marine biofouling, is characterized by the accretion of microorganisms,
20 plant matter, or aquatic fauna on submerged surfaces (Yebra et al., 2004). Although an extensive body
21 of scientific literature exists on this topic (Callow and Callow, 2002; Cao et al., 2011; Armstrong et al.,
22 2000; Yang et al., 2014), the global dilemma of biofouling in freshwater ecosystems is increasingly
23 commanding the focus of both scholars and policymakers (Nakanao and Strayer, 2014; Xu et al., 2013;
24 Liu et al., 2020). This rising concern stems from its profound ramifications on the performance and
25 durability of materials employed across a multitude of freshwater applications—from water purification
26 systems to quality monitoring apparatuses, and including freshwater vessel hulls (Wood and Marsh, 1999;

27 Khuram et al., 2014; Humbert and Törökkné, 2016). The capability of these materials to thwart freshwater
28 biofouling is pivotal for ensuring operational effectiveness and curtailing maintenance expenditures. As
29 such, elucidating the mechanistic underpinnings of freshwater biofouling and ascertaining materials that
30 can efficaciously mitigate it are crucial objectives.

31 While significant advancements have been made in the study of marine biofouling, including the
32 establishment of assessment protocols for anti-marine biofouling materials and summarization of
33 biofouling formation processes (Davidson et al., 2016; Voulvoulis et al., 2002; Menchaca et al., 2014),
34 there has been comparatively less focus on biofouling in freshwater systems. This lack of attention is not
35 merely due to the distinct fouling organisms and water chemistry in freshwater ecosystems, but also
36 because these differences present unique challenges in the development of anti-freshwater biofouling
37 materials (Karatayev et al., 2002; Mackie and Claudi, 2010; Callow 1993). As a result, there has yet to
38 emerge a broad-spectrum antifouling material effective in both freshwater and marine environments.
39 This highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive, multi-scale approach to evaluate materials'
40 resistance to freshwater biofouling.

41 This study aims to address the research gap by introducing an eight-stage experimental framework
42 designed to thoroughly investigate the mechanisms and challenges associated with biofouling in
43 freshwater systems. To this end, we employed a host of cutting-edge techniques and methods, including
44 differential interference contrast (DIC) microscopy, high-resolution digital single-lens reflex (DSLR)
45 macro photography, High-Speed Imaging Scanning Electron Microscopy (HIS-SiM), laser confocal
46 microscopy, atomic force microscopy (AFM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and advanced
47 artificial intelligence algorithms. This framework not only quantifies the intricate processes involved in
48 freshwater biofouling and assesses the anti-biofouling capabilities of various innovative materials, but
49 also delves into the micro- and macro-level dynamics of these processes. By adopting this multi-tiered,
50 interdisciplinary approach, the current study not only provides engineers and policymakers with direct,
51 practical insights for material selection but also lays a solid foundation for future research into the
52 complex biological, chemical, and physical processes underpinning biofouling. The ultimate goal is to
53 expedite the development of effective and environmentally sustainable anti-biofouling materials.

54 In freshwater ecosystems, biofouling is often initiated by the adhesion of algae to material surfaces,
55 including that of sensitive equipment such as sensors (Ozkan and Berberoglu, 2013). Algal cells adhere
56 to these surfaces by excreting extracellular polymeric substances, forming a preliminary biofilm that not

57 only encourages the colonization of additional microorganisms but also compromises the integrity and
 58 function of the material (Wijewardene et al., 2022; Sekar et al., 2004). In the case of sensors, algal fouling
 59 can result in significant data distortion, as the biofilm layer acts as a barrier that interferes with the
 60 sensor's ability to accurately measure parameters like pH, dissolved oxygen, and turbidity (as shown in
 61 Fig. 1). Over time, this distortion escalates, leading to increasing inaccuracies in data collection and
 62 requiring frequent maintenance. Furthermore, the persistent presence of biofouling imposes additional
 63 metabolic loads on the material, accelerating its degradation and significantly reducing its operational
 64 lifespan. Therefore, understanding the dynamics of algal adhesion in freshwater environments is crucial
 65 for mitigating the associated functional and economic costs.

66

67 Fig. 1. Sensors attached by biofouling after a period of immersion in freshwater systems.

68 In the present study, aimed at assessing the antifouling capabilities of materials in freshwater
 69 environments, we have constructed a comprehensive and systematic experimental procedure. This
 70 protocol consists of eight major steps: 1) Sampling & Identification, which involves the collection and
 71 preliminary identification of biofouling samples from freshwater locales; 2) Macro Photography,
 72 employing high-resolution DSLR cameras to capture the macroscopic state of microbial attachment on
 73 material surfaces; 3) Microfouling Observation, using HIS-SiM technology for microscopic observation
 74 of microfouling; 4) Protein & Polysaccharide Detection, utilizing confocal laser scanning microscopy
 75 along with specific staining techniques to identify proteins and polysaccharides within biofilms; 5)
 76 Biofilm Morphology, employing AFM for detailed observation of biofilm structures; 6) Biofilm

77 Adhesive Force, also using AFM with force-distance curve measurement modes to assess the adhesion
 78 forces of biofilms on different material surfaces; 7) Biofouling Cell Morphology, utilizing SEM equipped
 79 with an Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) spectrometer to examine and analyze the morphological
 80 and chemical composition of biofouling cells; and 8) Artificial Intelligence, leveraging advanced data
 81 analytics and machine learning algorithms to synthesize data collected from the previous seven steps, for
 82 predicting the types of organisms that may attach, their rates of attachment, as well as estimating the
 83 expected service life of the material. As illustrated in Fig. 2, these eight steps form a multi-layered, multi-
 84 dimensional evaluation system, aiming to provide an in-depth and comprehensive investigation into the
 85 antifouling capabilities of materials.

86
 87 Fig. 2. Process for assessing the resistance of materials to freshwater biofouling: Sampling &
 88 identification, Macro photography, Microfouling observation, Protein & polysaccharide detection,
 89 Biofilm morphology, Biofilm adhesive force, Biofouling cell morphology, and Artificial Intelligence.

90 Prior to the initiation of the first experimental phase, two crucial pretreatment steps are conducted for
 91 sample preparation and evaluation. The first pretreatment phase involves field sampling. The research
 92 team proceeds to sites with known freshwater biofouling to manually collect samples using tweezers
 93 from rocks covered with biofouling organisms. These samples are then placed, along with water, in a
 94 temperature-controlled box set at 4 degrees Celsius. Multi-point and random sampling may be performed
 95 to ensure the representativeness of the samples. Upon returning to the laboratory, these samples undergo

96 microscopic observation and identification, as well as potentially a series of chemical and molecular
97 biology analyses (Dobretsov and Rittschof, 2023; Kögler et al., 2016). These may include nutrient
98 content measurements, pH and dissolved oxygen quality parameters, and advanced genetic sequencing
99 to thoroughly understand the biofouling population structure, growth conditions, and ecological
100 characteristics.

101 The second pretreatment phase is sample cultivation. Biofouling organisms and water collected from
102 the field are transferred into specialized cultivation systems for a period ranging from 7 to 15 days. This
103 cultivation environment simulates natural lighting conditions, particularly the diurnal curve of light
104 intensity at sunrise and sunset. The temperature is maintained at a constant 25 degrees Celsius, considered
105 optimal for the growth of freshwater biofouling organisms (Cho et al., 2007). After a set period of
106 cultivation, samples are once again observed under the microscope and photographed. These new images
107 are compared with an algal reference database and contrasted with the identification results from the first
108 phase to observe any changes in the types of biofouling organisms. Both of these pretreatment stages are
109 vitally important; they not only provide essential baseline data for the subsequent experimental phases
110 but also facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the diversity and variability of biofouling in natural
111 environments. This knowledge further informs the research team's ability to more accurately assess the
112 antifouling capabilities of various materials in the succeeding experimental stages.

113 In the first phase of the experiment, high-resolution DSLR cameras were employed for macroscopic
114 photography. Samples were extracted at various time points and placed in a photography studio for
115 capturing, with the objective of meticulously documenting and visually assessing the dynamic process
116 of biological attachment on the sample surfaces. The primary advantage of this approach lies in its ability
117 to swiftly and intuitively identify which among the newly developed antifouling materials exhibit
118 exceptional resistance to biofouling. This serves as an initial screening for subsequent, more intricate
119 tests. However, the limitations of this phase reside in its inability to delve into microscopic explanations
120 or analyses for the observed phenomena and differences. As a preliminary evaluation tool, macroscopic
121 photography can offer directional guidance to researchers, but it must be complemented with more
122 detailed microscopic analyses for a comprehensive understanding of the situation.

123 In the second phase of the experiment, HIS-SiM was utilized to observe the microscopic biofouling
124 on the surfaces of various prepared samples. In contrast to the macroscopic photography employed in the
125 first phase, HIS-SiM allows for microscopic investigation of the complex structures and dynamic

126 processes of biological adhesion (Mo et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023). This technology features extremely
127 high spatial resolution and imaging speed, enabling precise observation and analysis of cell formations,
128 microbial communities, or biofilm development. Not only does this assist in identifying which material
129 performs better at the microscopic level in resisting biofouling, but it also helps to explore the
130 fundamental mechanisms behind biofouling adhesion. Consequently, the microscopic observations made
131 in this phase provide a more in-depth and detailed understanding of the anti-biofouling capabilities of
132 the prepared materials, filling the microscopic information gap left by the first phase of macroscopic
133 photography.

134 In the third phase of the experiment, confocal microscopy was employed to detect proteins and
135 polysaccharides. Through the use of specific dyes, such as Fluorescein 5-Isothiocyanate (FITC) and
136 Calcofluor white stain, proteins and polysaccharides within the biofilm can be distinctly marked and
137 identified. Confocal microscopy offers three-dimensional high-resolution images, allowing for precise
138 observation and quantification of the distribution and density of these biological macromolecules on
139 various material surfaces. This phase is crucial, as proteins and polysaccharides play a central role in the
140 formation of biofouling (Richards et al., 2020; Xiong and Liu, 2010). They are involved not only in the
141 initial adhesion of microbes but also contribute to the stability and maturation of the biofilm. Therefore,
142 through highly specific labeling and quantitative analysis, this phase enables a more comprehensive
143 understanding of the anti-biofouling properties of various materials and the molecular mechanisms
144 behind them. This provides a complementary analytical approach to the first two phases, offering a
145 multifaceted, in-depth understanding of biofouling phenomena as well as the effectiveness of the
146 prepared antifouling materials in the early stages of biofouling adhesion.

147 In the fourth phase of the experiment, AFM was employed to meticulously study the morphology of
148 biofilms and extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). The high resolution and three-dimensional
149 surface topography information offered by AFM allow us to observe in detail the microstructures of
150 biofilms formed during the early stages of biofouling, as well as associated morphological changes in
151 EPS. Notably, this phase also includes a detailed analysis of the composition of EPS, which comprises
152 polysaccharides, proteins, lipids, and other components, and their roles and significance in the early
153 stages of biofilm formation (Beech et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2022). Through this approach, we were able
154 to delve deeply into the interactions and arrangements between cells and EPS during biofilm formation,
155 and how these factors affect the antifouling performance of various materials. These observations and

156 analyses not only help us understand the early microscopic mechanisms behind biofouling but also
157 provide valuable insights for the development of more effective anti-biofouling materials. Therefore, this
158 phase provides a comprehensive and detailed perspective for evaluating and understanding the behavior
159 and morphological characteristics of biofouling on different material surfaces.

160 In the fifth phase of the experiment, continued to use AFM, but this time to assess the adhesion forces
161 of the biofilms formed during the early stages of biofouling through force-distance curve measurements.
162 The focus of this stage is to quantify the adhesion forces of early biofilms on various material surfaces.
163 By precisely measuring the interaction forces with the material surfaces, we can obtain more specific,
164 quantifiable information about the anti-biofouling capabilities of different materials. This method allows
165 for a more comprehensive mechanical analysis, which is invaluable for understanding the adhesion and
166 formation of biofilms. This information not only aids in understanding the anti-biofouling performance
167 of various materials but also provides crucial data for further research, such as why certain materials are
168 more effective in resisting biofouling and whether they are more easily removed in the early reversible
169 adhesion stage. In summary, through force-distance curve measurements, the fifth phase provides a
170 quantifiable, specific method for assessing the adhesive forces of biofilms, complementing the
171 morphological and compositional analyses of the previous phases.

172 In the sixth phase of the experiment, a SEM equipped with an EDS was employed to investigate the
173 morphology and chemical composition of fouled cells. This technology allows us not only to observe the
174 morphological differences of cells on fouled sample surfaces at high resolution but also to accurately
175 quantify and characterize their chemical components through EDS spectral analysis. This integrated
176 analysis aids in a more comprehensive understanding of the biofouling phenomenon, particularly
177 regarding the effects of different materials on cell adhesion and biofilm formation. Through detailed
178 observations of morphology and chemical composition, we can deeply understand which elements or
179 compounds play a leading role in the biofouling process and how they interact with different material
180 surfaces. This information not only assists us in evaluating the anti-biofouling performance of materials
181 but also provides valuable data for improving material design and developing more effective anti-fouling
182 strategies. Therefore, the sixth phase offers a multi-dimensional and highly nuanced evaluation method
183 through morphological and chemical composition analysis, further enriching our understanding of
184 biofouling.

185 In the final phase of the experiment, Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be employed to perform an
 186 integrated analysis and prediction of the data collected in the preceding stages. Utilizing specific machine
 187 learning or deep learning algorithms, dynamic adhesion rate curves for the relevant materials can be
 188 generated. This approach not only allows for a more precise and comprehensive analysis of existing data
 189 but also forecasts the types of species that may adhere to the material in the future, along with their
 190 respective adhesion rates. For instance, Bloomfield et al. (2021) trained a deep learning model using
 191 expert consensus to automatically evaluate biofouling in images. Additionally, AI algorithms can
 192 estimate the expected lifespan of the material, providing invaluable information for practical applications
 193 and material selection. For example, Mittendorf et al. (2023) assessed the impact of biofouling on ships
 194 via incremental machine learning, effectively reducing ship maintenance costs. By incorporating AI, we
 195 not only enhance our understanding of existing data but also expand our predictive capabilities for future
 196 biofouling behavior. This provides material scientists, engineers, and decision-makers with a robust tool
 197 for assessing the biofouling risks that different materials may face in actual environments, as well as the
 198 long-term durability of these materials. In summary, the integration of AI pushes the experiment into a
 199 new dimension that is rich in information and predictive capabilities, opening up new possibilities for
 200 research and application of anti-biofouling materials. A schematic of this assessment process is shown
 201 in Fig. 3.

202

203 Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the process of assessing the resistance of materials to freshwater biofouling.

204 While this study employs a meticulously designed, multi-stage, and multi-instrument experimental
205 framework, several challenges could affect the integrity and applicability of the findings. First and
206 foremost, each experimental phase, whether it involves HIS-SiM, confocal microscopy, or atomic force
207 microscopy, brings with it inherent technological limitations. These limitations could manifest as
208 potential errors in spatial resolution, imaging speed, sensitivity to biofilm components, or even biases
209 stemming from sample preparation procedures. This is particularly relevant in the phases employing
210 highly specialized techniques like force-distance curve measurements, where the quantification of
211 biofilm adhesion forces requires careful calibration. Secondly, the resource-intensive nature of this study
212 poses significant constraints. The high operational costs, time consumption, and specialized training
213 required for these advanced techniques may limit the scope and scale of the research. This is especially
214 pertinent when long-term monitoring and time-series data analysis are imperative for understanding the
215 complex, dynamic biofouling processes on various material surfaces. Thirdly, the generalizability of the
216 findings might be constrained due to field sampling limitations. Data representativeness could be
217 compromised by factors like seasonality, geographical variations, and sampling timing, which could
218 influence the types of microbial communities adhering to material surfaces and subsequently affecting
219 biofouling rates.

220 The study, nevertheless, offers a robust, multi-layered evaluation framework for examining
221 biofouling in a freshwater context. The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence for data analytics adds an
222 additional layer of sophistication, allowing for enhanced data interpretability and predictive modeling.
223 However, future studies should seek to address these technological and methodological gaps. This could
224 potentially involve the incorporation of more cutting-edge imaging modalities, automated sample
225 processing pipelines, and machine learning-based data analytics algorithms tailored for biofouling
226 assessment. In the long term, this experimental framework could be adapted and extended to a variety of
227 application scenarios and material types. It holds great promise for becoming a standardized
228 methodology for assessing and mitigating freshwater biofouling, especially when augmented with more
229 sophisticated data analytics platforms and predictive modeling techniques.

230

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234 **Data and scripts availability**

235 Data are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10080999>

236 Scripts are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074397>

237 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

238 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in 454
239 relation to the content of the article.

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